

Battling the Infodemics: Health Communication Effectiveness During COVID-19

Authors: *Iryna Sabat, Nirosha Elsem Varghese, Sebastian Neumann-Böhme, Pedro Pita Barros, Werner Brouwer, Job van Exel, Jonas Schreyögg, and Tom Stargardt*

ABSTRACT

Introduction: The coronavirus disease (COVID-19) outbreak in many parts of the world has triggered serious threats to public health. During this period of crisis, the World Health Organization (WHO) reminded all countries and communities that the spread of this virus could be significantly slowed through the implementation of robust containment and control measures. In light of this, the role of public health bodies in communicating the right message and in the right form to the public seems crucial.

In our study, we aim to assess the effectiveness of communication strategies used by international and national public health authorities to inform the public on COVID-19 risks and prevention. We conducted a survey experiment on nationally representative samples of adults from seven European countries (N=7500) to test the efficacy of public health messages in a form of prevention information provision emphasizing either individual or societal benefit of adherence to such measures. The study seeks to investigate how people's risk perceptions and behaviors change subject to the preventive information provision as compared to the control group.

The findings of this research will be relevant for policymakers and public health professionals in the development of effective communication strategies during disease outbreaks.